

Computational analysis of composites with 2D nanoreinforcement (Mxene, Graphene)

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Nanoreinforced polymers are considered among most promising materials for energy, aerospace, marine and automotive applications. The possibilities of drastic enhancement of the mechanical properties and strength of polymers and composites by using nanoreinforcement attracted great interest of the research community. One of most promising groups of nanoreinforcements are 2D nanoparticles among them, graphene, graphene oxides and MXenes [1][2].

In this paper, we review the micromechanical models of polymer composites, reinforced with 2D nanoscale particles. The layer of perturbed polymer around small nanoparticles is represented as third material layer (effective interface concept) [4][7][8]. Figure 1 shows a schema of the micromechanical idealization of MXene as a three-layer platelet.

Figure 1. Micromechanical idealization of MXene as a three-layer platelet [5][6]

3D computational models of nanocomposites are presented and reviewed. Initiation and growth of microcracks in the nanoclay reinforced polymer composites is analyzed in numerical experiments using 3D micromechanical unit cell models. Figure 2 shows the computational model of the crack development in a polymer composite with aligned graphene reinforcement [7][8].

Physical parameters such as nanoplatelet aspect ratio, clustering and orientation that affect the damage performance of nanocomposites are studied systematically, and the recommendations toward to enhancement of the materials properties by varying the microstructures are developed.

Figure 2. Computational model of the crack development in a polymer composite with graphene reinforcement [7][8]

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